

Vietnamese popular religion

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Vietnamese popular religion (tín ngưỡng dân gian Việt Nam) is the most popular faith system in Vietnam although many official religions have been existing. Confucianism was mainly adopted by the royal court and elites, while the folks localized and transformed it into “mass Confucianism” (see Nguyen 2016, 2020). Although Buddhism was promoted to state religion between the 11th and 14th centuries, at the grassroots level, folk Buddhism with a folk religious flavor still dominates (see Duong 2004; McHale 2004). There are four main reasons for the formation and development of Vietnamese folk religion, including (1) The limited knowledge of nature and life made ancient Vietnamese revere, worship, and seek shelter from “superpowers”; (2) Rice-growing traditions made pre-modern Vietnamese people largely dependent on nature and superpower forces; (3) Local wisdom has been often absorbed and ritualized into popular religions; and (4) The folk culture stream based on folk beliefs coexists with the official culture stream dominated by the royal family, and there is an interactive relationship of opposition and complementarity between the two. Vietnamese folk religion is divided into three categories, namely family, community, and nation-state worship. Among families, the most prominent are the customs of ancestor worship and the veneration of Ngũ tự gia đường (Door Gods, Kitchen God, Guardian God, Well God, and Main Hall god (now replaced by God of Wealth), all following the standardized policy of the pre-modern monarch monarchies. Additionally, some families enshrine Saint Trần Hưng Đạo (see Phạm 2009), Quan Đế/Guandi and/or Quan Âm/the Bodhisattva of Compassion (Southern Vietnam) in their homes. At the community level, Vietnamese people practice animism and worship nature and human spirits, including those they believe control weather phenomena (Tứ pháp: Four goddesses who control clouds, rain, thunder, and lightning), space gods (including Tứ bất tử/the Four Immortals (Tản Viên, Chử Đồng Tử, Thánh Gióng, and Liễu Hạnh), Tam Phủ-Tứ phủ (see Nguyen 2002; Nguyen & Fjelstad 2018), Ngũ hổ tướng/the Five Tigers, etc.), sun god, moon goddess, star gods, mountain gods, water gods (such as Bà Thủy, Bà Cậu, Hà Bà), sea gods (General Đại Càn Nam Hải /Whales), God of Agriculture (Thần Nông), goddess of treasury (see Le 2007), snake gods (ông Lốt, Thanh xà - Bạch xà), classic imaginary figures (dragon, kirin, phoenix, etc.), tree gods, linga and yoni symbols, and others (see Trần 2001; Ngô 2018). When the Vietnamese migrated to the central and southern regions, they adopted and localized some of the beliefs of other ethnic groups to a certain extent, such as Goddess Po Nagar and Whale gods from the Chăm, Goddess Bà Đen, Bà Chúa Xứ/Goddess of Realm in Mekong Delta (see Taylor 2004), and Ông Tà/Neak Ta from the Khmer, Quan Đế/Guandi, Thiên Hậu/Tianhou, God of Wealth, and others from the Chinese. In pre-colonial periods, every village had to worship thần Thành hoàng (Village Guardian God - a miniature symbol of the king in every village's communal house (đình làng) (see Ngo & Nguyen 2020). There are many customs of hero worship in Vietnamese folk religious system, such as the cults of Thánh Gióng, An Dương Vương, Hai Bà Trưng, Bà Triệu, Trần Hưng Đạo (northern region), Quang Trung (central region), Trương Định, Thủ Khoa Huân, Lê Tấn Kiều, Trần Văn Thành, Nguyễn Huỳnh Đức, Võ Thị Sáu, etc. (southern region). From the late 19th century to the early 20th century, under French rule, the religious salvation movements became active in the southern region, and folk religions (especially ancestor worship and hero worship) actively joined Buddhism, Taoism, and others to form various sects and new religions such as Bửu Sơn Kỳ Hương, Tứ Ân Hiếu Nghĩa, Phật giáo Hòa Hảo, Tứ Ân Đạo Phật, Minh Đức Nho giáo đại đạo, Caodaism, Minh Sư Đạo, and so on (see Ho Tai 1983; Do 2003; Truong 2016; Nguyen 2020; Nguyen et al. 2024). Vietnam's 53 ethnic minorities still retain their traditions of folk beliefs, increasing the diversity of Vietnam's religious culture. At the state level, the custom of offering sacrifices to heaven and earth has a long history during the pre-modern periods. At the end of the 19th century, the Vietnamese people formed the national cult of Hùng Kings and designated the tenth day of the third lunar month as the anniversary of those national founders. Lạc Long Quân and Âu Cơ (the legendary parents of the first Hùng King, recorded by Vietnamese historians during the 13-15 periods) were

officialized as the Founding Father and Mother. At the end of the 20th century, the worship of Ho Chi Minh was formed nationwide while the Ho Chi Minh Mausoleum was built in Hanoi (see Nguyễn 2017). In addition, the Vietnamese people also worship meritorious kings such as Đinh Tiên Hoàng, Lê Hoàn, Lý Thái Tổ, Trần Thái Tông, Quang Trung, meritorious generals such as Lý Thường Kiệt, Trần Hưng Đạo, Võ Nguyên Giáp, etc. as well as meritorious cultural experts such as Chu Văn An, Nguyễn Trãi, Nguyễn Bình Khiêm, Nguyễn Du, Nguyễn Đình Chiểu, and so on.

Date Range: 0 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Vietnam

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Vietnam

Vietnam

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Lĩnh Nam Chính Quái
- Source 2: Việt Điện U Linh Tập
- Source 3: Ngô Đức Thịnh. 2018. Tín ngưỡng và lễ hội cổ truyền Việt Nam (Vietnamese folk beliefs and festivals). Hanoi: Tri thức.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://vietnam.opendevlopmentmekong.net/topics/overview-of-religions-in-vietnam/>
- Source 2 URL: <https://asiasociety.org/education/religion-vietnam>
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2024/06/17/practices/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://vjol.info.vn/index.php/rsr>
- Source 1 Description: This is the website of the Journal of Religion Studies
- Source 2 URL: <https://vanhoatinnguoc.vn/bai-viet/tin-nguong-viet-mang-tinh-dan-toc-dan-gian-4232.html>
- Source 2 Description: This is the official website of the Institute of Vietnamese popular religion
- Source 3 URL: <https://frs.ussh.vnu.edu.vn/vi/news/tac-gia-tac-pham/tin-nguong-va-quan-ly-nha-nuoc-doi-voi-hoat-dong-tin-nguong-128.html>
- Source 3 Description: This is the official website of the Department of Religious Studies, University of Social Sciences and Humanities, Vietnam National University - Hanoi

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Vietnamese popular religion coexists with various official religions, including Buddhism, Hoahaoism, Caodaism, etc. There is no clear sign of competition between popular religion and other religions in cultural contact between them.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese popular religion is a system of various mutually interactive faiths and beliefs.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: In general, religious interactions/communications in Vietnam are neutral and peaceful.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Violent conflict has been rare in Vietnam (see Vo Van Sen & Nguyen Ngoc Tho. 2020. "Crossing boundaries and state-building: harmonization and tolerance in Vietnamese religions", *International Journal of Asia-Pacific Studies* 16(2): 59-83.)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The state, in general, shows unofficial support to ancestor worship and some popular beliefs such as Tam phủ - Tứ phủ, Bà Chúa Xứ, etc.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Various popular cults exist, and each has countless followers.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Vietnamese people have diverse religious beliefs except for Catholicism, Christianity and Islam, so it is difficult to count the number of believers of each popular religion.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Notes: Vietnamese popular religion was formed and consolidated on the basis of absorbing various official religions, especially Buddhism, Confucianism, Daoism, and others.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Various folk beliefs are widely spread throughout the country and have not formed a systematic organization. Only a few important beliefs, such as Bà chúa Kho cult in Bắc Ninh and Bà chúa Xứ Núi Sam in An Giang, have established executive boards to manage local religious activities.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: With the exception of some singular popularized religious sects such as Minh Đức Nho giáo đại đạo, Minh Sư đạo, etc., other folk beliefs have no classics/scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Some popular beliefs have got its main temple complex, such as Bà chúa Kho Temple in Bắc Ninh City, Trần Hưng Đạo Temple in Nam Định City, Po Inu Nagar Temple complex in Nha Trang, Bà Chúa Xứ Temple in Châu Đốc City, etc., other folk beliefs have small religious institutions or no temples (i.e. family beliefs).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Except for family ancestral graveyards.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Other popular beliefs in Vietnam, in addition to family-related beliefs such as ancestor worship, Ngũ tự gia đường, etc., often have small and medium-sized religious facilities in local areas.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Almost all folk gods and ancestors have their own altars, where people make offerings and sacrifices regularly.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Vietnamese people have maintained their folk beliefs for thousands of years and have a firm faith. There are no clear devotional markers in Vietnamese culture, but people have a deep faith in their ancestors and gods.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Many popular tempels have become significant pilgrimage centers. Dozens of thousand of people may gather to celebrate significant ceremonies/rituals at Bà Chúa Kho Temple, Trần Hưng Đạo Temple in Nam Định, Bà Thiên Hậu Temple in Thủ Dầu Một, Quan Đế Temple in Phan Thiết, and Bà Chúa Xứ Temple in Châu Đốc, etc. Among the popular beliefs, the Bà Chúa Xứ Temple in Châu Đốc, Bà Thiên Hậu Temple in Thủ Dầu Một, and Trần Hưng Đạo Temple in

Nam Định attract between one and four million pilgrims and participants during their annual festival seasons.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Po Inu Nagar Temple complex in Nha Trang & Bà Đen temple complex

Notes: Po Nagar Temple complex in Nha Trang is originally a Chăm Hindu/Brahmanic center in the ancient time. It has got many monumental structures, including a cluster of three Hinduic temples at the heart of the complex. The cult of Bà Đen in Tây Ninh Province was adopted by the Vietnamese from local Khmer community three centuries ago. Bà Đen Temple was built on the side of Bà Đen Mountain and has become a famous pilgrimage point among Vietnamese people. In 2020, the large-scaled Tây Bồng Đà Sơn Avalokitesvara Statue was erected on the top of the mountain and the surrounding area has become a tourism spot, with the old and well-known Bà Đen temple becoming its subsidiary.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: Ngũ tự gia đường gods' and ancestors' tablets and photos are worshipped at home, while statues and/or portraits of gods and goddesses are worshipped at public temples. There are no statues or images of the goddess in Po Nagar Temple in Nha Trang, instead people worship the Linga-Yoni structure in the main hall in accordance with the Chăm's Hindu tradition. Bà Chúa Xứ statue in Châu Đốc is a transformation of a long-standing Shiva statue in the ancient local Hindu/Brahmanic tradition.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Different folk beliefs have different iconographic features.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Some folk groups built major folk religious sites on hills or mountains, making the area a sacred religious center, such as Po Nagar Temple in Nha Trang (Khánh Hòa province), Bà Đen Temple in Tây Ninh province, and Bà Chúa Xứ Temple in Châu Đốc (An Giang province).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Certain folk beliefs have strong pilgrimage activities, such as Hùng King belief, Bà Chúa Kho belief, Trần Hưng Đạo belief, Bà chúa Xứ belief, Bà Thiên Hậu belief, etc.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: People believed that heroes and family ancestors who had made great contributions had power in the afterlife.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Vietnamese folk religion is deeply influenced by popular Buddhism, and people generally believe in Buddhist concepts such as cause and effect, and reincarnation in the next life. However, there is no specific spatial location for the afterlife.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Influenced by Buddhism, many folk believers believe that people who do good deeds can be reborn as humans in the next life. Many people also believe that heroes with merits

become powerful gods (i.e., Trần Hưng Đạo, Hồ Chí Minh, etc.).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Burial of heroes and ancestors are exceptionally arranged.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The gods of Vietnamese folk beliefs are all anthropomorphic, with the exception of the Chăm-rooted Po Inu Nagar goddess.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: In certain faiths, people believe that certain gods are heavenly gods, such as Mẫu thượng ngàn in the Tam phủ-Tứ phủ goddess belief, Ngọc Hoàng (Emperor of Heaven), Bà Thiên Hậu goddess in the Hoa people, etc.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In folk beliefs, people believe that there are all kinds of demons and monsters in the underworld, but the highest god in the underworld (Diêm vương) comes from

popular Buddhism.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: But there are exceptions, such as the worship of the Hùng Kings, the worship of the Hai Bà Trưng, the worship of meritorious kings, and the worship of Heavenly Emperor.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: In premodern times, according to Confucian perspective, Vietnamese kings were seen as "sons of Heavenly Emperor".

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Except for the old Confucian belief that the kings were the sons of the Emperor of Heaven.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: The cult of Thần Thành hoàng/Village Guardian gods

Notes: In the pre-modern period, the imperial court supported the worship of Thành hoàng gods in various villages and issued policies to formalize them, making them the image symbol of the king at the grassroots level. The cult of thần Thành hoàng advocated for loyalty, virtue cultivation, and social order in each village.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people have traditionally aligned their moral aspirations and desire for prosperity with divine power, so the supreme god is considered unquestionably good.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Vietnamese folk beliefs are biased towards women, with goddesses being worshipped more than gods.

Notes: Vietnamese folk beliefs are biased towards women, with goddesses being worshipped more than gods. Therefore, many goddesses in Vietnamese culture are goddesses of benevolence, who grant fertility, prosperity and good harvests to people.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that all gods are powerful and knowledgeable, but they tend to locate each god in a specific domain of human affairs, such as the Earth God "in charge of houses and land" while the God of Wealth "grants good luck in business."

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Typically the worship of Tứ pháp goddesses, eg., Pháp Vân, Pháp Vũ, Pháp Lôi, and Pháp Điện, each of which controls various aspects of the weather: clouds, rain, thunder and lightning. In southern Vietnam, people worship the Earth God of Land and the God of Wealth together at the same altar in their homes, and each god is believed to bless people in a specific area (housing/farmland, and business).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Followers of a particular monolith (e.g. Bà Chúa Xứ, Bà Đen, etc.) believe that the knowledge of the god/goddess is unlimited.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Exception: the symbol of the Emperor of Heaven appears in Daoism and many folk beliefs.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese people believe that gods have great power and knowledge and can observe people from all over the place.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese people believe that gods can see and feel every action of human beings everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese people believe that gods can see through people's heart-mind and apply the principle of cause and effect to them.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people believe that gods knows all of their thoughts, characters, and actions.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people often say ""người đang làm, trời đang nhìn (gods are watching what you do)". People believe that gods knows all of their thoughts, characters, and actions, so they can control every aspect of people's lives.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Vietnamese people believe that gods are to protect the harmonious circulation of the cosmos and social order.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese gods, especially the Heavenly Emperor, reward those who do good deeds with good fortune and prosperity in the years to come.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: People who do not do good are afraid of being punished. People in ancient times believed that droughts and floods were punishments from gods on villagers who did not live morally or did not do enough good deeds. In Ho Chi Minh City before 1975 [Saigon], people both sides involved in civil lawsuits came to General Governor Lê Văn Duyệt Temple in Bình Thạnh District to take an oath. People who committed mistakes/crimes did not dare to do so because they believed that he (General Governor Lê Văn Duyệt) would punish them.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Many legends and stories emphasize the care and positive emotion of the gods for those who do good.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Various legends and stories tell of the gods' anger and punishment on those who committed sins.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes
Notes: All popular religions in Vietnam are polytheistic.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes
Notes: Some believers may sense that god(s) is “with” and “watching” them in their daily lives.
- ↳ In dreams:
– Yes
Notes: Some people tell stories about receiving guidance and blessings from gods in their dreams. Meanwhile stories about god's punishment are also widespread to educate the mass.
- ↳ In trance possession:
– Yes
Notes: Spirit mediumship (lên đồng/nhập xác] is popular in specific cults in Vietnam, such as Tam phủ - Tứ phủ, Quan Đế, etc.. Some people believe that spirits "appear" and "communicate" with people through mediums.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to spirit mediumship, religious figures in many places also engage in forms of divination such as yin-yang divination so that people can "communicate" and "seek" guidance or direction from the gods in social affairs.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Some Vietnamese people believe that gods can directly "appear" in their dreams or may "communicate" with them through mediums.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The concept of Thiên nhân hợp nhất/Tianrenheyi in the old time

Notes: In ancient times, influenced by Confucianism, leaders of an uprising had to prove the Mandate of Heaven (Thiên mệnh) before ascending the throne. As a result, many stories emerged saying that the Heavenly Emperor bestowed them with the Mandate of Heaven and allowed them to kill the enemies and ascend the throne as kings.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: Normally no, even some people said they saw their ancestors, gods, or ghosts sometime.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: People can feel only in their heart-mind.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: This is a vague concept. Although people do not claim that their ancestors had extensive knowledge of the world, they do not emphasize that meritorious heroes also have such knowledge. Only supernatural beings have such knowledge.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people hold banquets and invite deceased ancestors to celebrate Tết (Lunar New Year) or attend important family ceremonies (weddings, funerals, death anniversaries) to bless the family and future generations. In many cases, people also believe that meritorious heroes will accompany and bless the community and the country.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that meritorious heroes like Saint Trần Hưng Đạo may punish those who commit sins.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that the karma of ancestors influences the prosperity and development of future generations.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Stories about heroic deeds are widely circulated among the people (some untrue facts are “newly-invented”), while family stories can vividly remind future generations of the achievements and good deeds of their ancestors.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Meritorious heroes and family ancestors are told to have more positive emotion in people's heart-mind.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Wandering spirits are often depicted as those who pose a threat to humanity.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: During the Tết (Lunar New Year) festival or important family ceremonies, people feel the presence of their ancestors. They must offer sacrifices and burn incense to worship and respect their ancestors.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Many people tell stories of dreams in which they meet and communicate with deceased ancestors, gods, or ghosts.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, people tell stories of “flying” to see their ancestors or spirits in their dreams and communicating with them.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Some families perform spiritual divination to “invite” deceased ancestors home and “communicate” with them through a medium, while some groups perform similar activities to “invite” heroic spirits and “communicate” with them.

↳ Only through specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: People perform various forms with or without specialists' assistance.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Only in ancient times would the king set up a divination ritual to “seek the advice of the gods” before making major national decisions such as anti-aggression wars. In Trà Vinh, specialists of Minh Đức Nho giáo đại đạo Sect perform similar rituals to “seek Confucius' advice” on the affairs of religious groups. Many Hoa/Chinese communities in southern Vietnam also hold similar ceremonies to seek support from God Quan Đế/Guandi or Goddess Thiên Hậu/Tianhou.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Family ceremonies

Notes: During the Tết Festival or major family ceremonies (such as weddings, funerals, death anniversaries, etc.), people believe that their ancestors will return home and “communicate” with them through the space of incense smoke.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are invisible, although they are depicted in statues and portraits.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It depends on each devotee's faith.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Followers of supernatural cults believe that their gods/spirits are focused on specific aspects of life, such as a rain goddess focuses on controlling rain, a river goddess focuses on controlling water, and so on.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that community spirits are the incarnations of officials who manage the spiritual life of the community in a certain area, so these spirits understand and control the spiritual life of all residents in the area. For example, Bà chúa Xứ in Châu Đốc is called the Goddess of Realm.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Many community gods are believed to have unrestricted knowledge and power, such as Saint Trần Hưng Đạo, Tam phủ-Tứ phủ goddesses, Bà Chúa Xứ, etc.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Some popular gods have unrestricted knowledge and power, such as

the Heavenly Emperor.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: People believe that supernatural beings such as the Heavenly Emperor, Thượng ngàn Goddess, and others may see them everywhere in public.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Various gods are believed to have power to see people everywhere, even in dark or at home.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that supernatural gods rule their souls, so they can see into their souls and heart-mind.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Many people believe that supernatural gods have the power to observe their character and apply cause-effect principle.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: People believe that gods know all what they do, but not sure about what they will do.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The gods are believed to have the power to reward those who do good. The kitchen god is thought to report every year on the good and bad deeds of the family to the Heavenly Emperor, who would reward or punish the family in the coming year based on that report.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: People believe that gods have the power to punish. In ancient times, many people believed that droughts and floods were the result of the loss of morality of villagers/communities. Therefore, villagers used to held grand ceremonies to pray for the blessing, protection, and salvation of the gods.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people believe that the supernatural gods are benevolent and always have positive feelings towards people who do good.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that if the community "loses its collective moral integrity", the gods may become angry and punish it (drought, floods, disease, etc.).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Vietnamese people believe that heroic gods and family ancestors are always great protectors.

Notes: The heroic gods, for instance, Saint Trần Hưng Đạo, who defeated the Yuan-Mongol armies three times in the 13th century, is believed to spiritually protect the country, while ancestors are considered great protectors of the family.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: Excepting for the ancestor worship.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Each religious sect has its own hierarchy, with main god(s) and attendant deities. The custom of worshipping the Jade Emperor of Heaven is an example. He has a large group of followers (such as Nam Tào, Bắc Đẩu, Thiên Lô, and others) who help him rule the world. The cult of Thần Thành hoàng (Village Guardian god) in each village follows a similar pattern. The Tam phủ - Tứ phủ goddess belief in the Red River Delta is also similar.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Some supernatural deities are limited to specific areas, such as the Pháp Vân/cloud goddess who controls only the clouds; Pháp Vũ/the rain god who controls the rain; the Earth God who controls houses and farmland, etc. Regional gods have broader powers and can control all aspects of life, such as Bà Chúa Xứ in Châu Đốc, Bà Đen in Tây Ninh, etc.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Notes: Each folk belief has its own order, but its structure is not formally fixed, with the exception of the Heavenly Emperor cult, which has been absorbed from popular Daoism.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Gods, such as the Heavenly Emperor, Bà chúa Xứ, and others are believed to have power of monitoring prosocial norm adherence.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

Notes: Vietnam's various folk beliefs coexist harmoniously, with no significant conflicts between them or with other religious sects.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: So far, there has been no major conflict between folk beliefs and other systems.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: Normally this is not necessary, but it is believed that the person conducting the ceremony must abstain from sexual action for at least three days before the ceremony.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is an immoral act and people believe that gods will punish liars.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Notes: This is not mandatory; however, believers are free to swear and pledge allegiance to gods and moral loyalty to society in order to seek gods' protection and blessings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people believe that gods only protect and bless hard-working people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Hầu đồng mediumship in northern Vietnam (such as Tam phủ-Tứ phủ belief) and Múa bóng rỗi performances (in goddess belief, such as Bà Chúa Xứ) are practiced popularly as methods to "communicate" with gods. In some rural areas, communities use witchcraft as part of their spiritualist practices.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
 - Notes: From the perspective of Vietnamese folk religion, disrespecting elders is an immoral act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
 - Notes: All crimes are immoral acts that people believe will be punished by gods.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Although there are no clear regulations, people follow ancient rules and principles when performing or participating in ceremonies.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: People believe that through proper and regular sacrificial activities, they can maintain respect for the gods and thus obtain their blessings.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: People almost think that gods' punishment is the consequence of unethical behavior of an individual or community.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Both group norms and social order

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese folk beliefs are deeply influenced by Buddhist philosophy, thus many emphasize punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: People believed that immoral people might be punished physically in the afterlife.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the severity of the unethical behavior.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: As being deeply influenced by mass Buddhism, Vietnamese people believe that those who commit serious immoral acts will be reincarnated as animals or lower life forms..

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that the law of cause and effect also applies in this real life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: People believe that bad luck will befall those who commit sins.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: People believe that collective immoral behavior may cause severe weather, drought, floods, diseases, etc., resulting in reduced crop yields and threats to people's lives.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Although it is only a vague idea, some people believe that serious unethical behavior can lead to traffic accidents or career and business failure.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that those who commit minor sins may be punished with some kind of punishment such as minor illness, physical injury, etc.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that people who commit serious crimes may be punished with some kind of punishment such as death, broken bones, blindness, etc.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on how serious the crimes/sins are.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the severity of the unethical behavior.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that a person's good or bad deeds may affect the fate of his descendants three generations later.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese believe that if a person does good deeds, the gods will protect his soul from evil spirits in the underworld.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Influenced by Buddhism, some folk religion believers believe that gods will bless them with eternal happiness in the afterlife.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: Influenced by Buddhism, some folk religion believers believe that they will be reborn in a better life form in the next life if they do major good deeds in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that people who do great good things, such as heroes, can become gods, saints, or go to heaven after death.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Followers of folk religions believe that by doing good deeds, they will have good harvests, good business, and a good life, and their children will receive a good education and career.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: For example, good crops, good business, and a prosperous family are the main good fortunes a person can obtain by doing good deeds in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Folk religious groups do not value political success or power.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The Vietnamese people believe that as long as everyone does good deeds, the supreme gods of Heaven and Earth will surely bless the country and help it defeat foreign enemies.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: People believe that the Heavenly Emperor and other gods will bless the country with peace and prosperity if they do good.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Many people believe that ethical behavior and proper ceremonies will ensure gods' reward of good weather, healthy crops, good business, and family prosperity.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: People believe that ethical behavior and proper ceremonies will bring people good journeys in life and living activities.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Some people believe that moral behavior and conduct will bring them wisdom and mental health.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people often say "They must live well and leave blessings for their descendants (sống tốt để lại phúc đức cho con cháu)".

- ↳ Other [specify]
- Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

- Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Notes: All Vietnamese folk beliefs emphasize moral behavior and ethical actions in life.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

- Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

- Yes

Notes: Honesty/truth, goodness and beauty are the three highest values.

↳ Courage (in battle):

- Field doesn't know

Notes: This is unclear norm in Vietnamese folk beliefs.

↳ Courage (generic):

- Yes

Notes: Vietnamese people believe that an ethical man can be strongly confident in life (i.e., doing business), because he is "supported by gods and ancestors".

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Folk beliefs often god-related encourage mutual compassion, kindness, and benevolence. People regularly hold ceremonies and festivals to practice these virtues.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: This is one of significant ethics in Vietnamese folk beliefs.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Sense of sharing is strongly encouraged among folk worship believers.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Altruism is an important virtue in the mind of a believers.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: In some folk beliefs, such as the worship of the saint Trần Hưng Đạo and the worship of Quan Đứ/Guandi, a sense of righteousness is emphasized.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Filial piety is one of the significant virtues in Vietnamese folk beliefs that is deeply influenced by Confucianism.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: In some folk beliefs, such as the worship of the saint Trần Hưng Đạo and the worship of meriteous heroes, loyalty (to family/community and country) is emphasized.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: One of major functions of Vietnamese folk beliefs (through faith, rituals, and festival activities) is social solidarity and cooperative mentality.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese folk beliefs guide individuals to participate and interact in the community; therefore, everyone is encouraged to develop self-discipline.

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Especially among the worship of thần Thành hoàng (Village Guardian gods) in northern Vietnam, wrestling matches or competitions for specific symbols are often held during village festivals to encourage young people to exercise.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese believers often feel a sense of peace and tranquility after after making a pilgrimage or attending a festival, as they believe the spirits will always protect and bless them.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese believers often feel happy and hopeful after making a pilgrimage or attending a festival, as they believe the gods will be always at their side.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese folk beliefs emphasize gratitude. Many Vietnamese people who have had prosperous business throughout the year will return to the temple to worship and thank the gods at the end of the year.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Only the ritual master is required to abstain from sex for at least three days before the ritual.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Limited folk beliefs have taboos on food. For example, when worshiping Quan Đế/Guandi, people are not allowed to use chicken as an offering.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Only mediums in certain folk beliefs in rural areas (i.e. Thiên Hậu and Quan Đế festivals in the lower Mekong Delta) inflict painful physical wounds (penetration of cheeks and lips, etc.) as part of local shamanic rituals.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Excepting for the spirit mediums in specific ceremonies in rural areas in the lower Mekong Delta.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: In particular, the worship of Thần thành hoàng/the village guardian gods requires villagers to accept the village's moral precepts and collective conventions.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Major ceremonies are held every year and believers can participate voluntarily.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It depends on each folk belief. The worship of Hùng Kings is common throughout the country. Ancestor worship is practiced on a family basis. The worship of thần Thành hoàng/Village Guardian gods is practiced on a village basis and is more popular in northern Vietnam. Other communal folk beliefs are formed in specific regions/areas and mainly attract local believers.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Many public belief executive committees are organized to provide charitable work, often with the support of local authorities.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They need to register with the local government or just request approval.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: They may provide food or other forms of charitable work on a voluntary basis.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Some public belief executive committee may provide financial support to build/modify rural transportation infrastructure (i.e., road, bridge, free ambulance service, free medical cares, fresh water supply systems, etc.)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They need to register with local government and/or request approval.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Unless they use the temple money to invest in business.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Believers are required to abide by national military regulations.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: National language chữ Quốc ngữ is used in all cases, excepting for specific rituals of ethnic minorities (Hoa, Tày, Thái, Hmong, Chăm, Khmer, Ê-đê, etc.).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Do, Thien. *Vietnamese Supernaturalism: Views from the Southern Region*. London & New York: RoutledgeCurzon., 2013.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Endres, W. Kirsten. *Performing the Divine: Mediums, Markets and Modernity in Urban Vietnam*. Copenhagen: NIAS Press; Nordic Institute of Asian Studies monograph series, no. 118., 2011.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Ninh, Thien-Huong. "Review: *performing the Divine: Mediums, Markets, and Modernity in Urban Vietnam*, by Kirstin W. Endres" 7, no. 4 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1525/vs.2012.7.4.154>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Tai, H. TH.. *Millenarianism and Peasant Politics in Vietnam*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1983. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674433700>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Lý, Lê Hồng. "Praying for Profit: The Cult of the Lady of the Treasury (*Chúa Kho*)" 38, no. 3 (October 2007). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022463407000239>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Duong, N. Dung . "An Exploration of Vietnamese Confucian Spirituality: The Idea of the Unity of the Three Teachings (*tam Giao Dong Nguyen*).” in”. In *Confucian Spirituality*, Vol. 2. edited by Tu Weiming, and Mary Evelyn Tucker, pp. 289–318. New York: Crossroad Publication Company, 2004.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, McHale, Shawn Frederick . *Print and Power: Confucianism, Communism, and Buddhism in the Making of Modern Vietnam*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press , 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1086/ahr/109.5.1550-a>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Ngo, Thi Phuong Lan, and Ngoc Tho Nguyen. "Continuity and Transformation of Rural Communal Temples in Vietnam: A Case Study of Tân Chánh Village, Long an Province" 17, no. 2 (July 30, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.21315/ijaps2021.17.2.10>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Đức Thịnh, Ngô. "Tin Ngưỡng Bà Chúa Kho Và Sự Biến Đổi Của Xã Hội Việt Nam". *Tạp Chí Nghiên Cứu Tôn Giáo* 16, no. 4 (November 7, 2008).

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Ngô, Đức Thịnh. *Tin Ngưỡng Và Lễ Hội Cổ Truyền Việt Nam (vietnamese Folk Beliefs and Festivals)*. Hanoi: Tri thức., 2018.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Tho, Nguyen Ngoc. "Confucianism and Humane Education in Contemporary Vietnam" 3, no. 4 (December 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40636-016-0076-8>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyen, Tho Ngoc, and Phong Thanh Nguyen. "Philosophical Transmission and Contestation" 8, no. 2 (May 20, 2020). <https://doi.org/10.4312/as.2020.8.2.79-112>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyen, Ngoc Tho. "When the Sage Becomes a God: The Confucian Sect of Minh Duc Nho Giao Dai Dao.". *Asian Studies* 8, no. 2 (2020): 17-50.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyen, Thanh Phong, Ngoc Tho Nguyen, and Trung Hieu Nguyen. "Mobilizacija Novih Področij" 12, no. 3 (September 3, 2024). <https://doi.org/10.4312/as.2024.12.3.65-100>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyễn, Thị Đức. *Tục Thờ Bác Ở Đồng Bằng Sông Cửu Long (the Cult of Uncle Ho Chi Minh in the Mekong River Delta)*. Ho Chi Minh City: Văn hóa Văn nghệ., 2017.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Fjelstad, Karen, and Nguyen Thi Hien, eds.. *Possessed by the Spirits*. Edited by Karen Fjelstad and Nguyen Thi Hien. Cornell University Press, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.7591/9781501719141>.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyen, Thi Hien. *The Religion of the Four Palaces: Mediumship and Therapy in Viet Culture*. Indianapolis: Indiana University Press., 2002.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Pham, Quynh Phuong. *Hero and Deity: Tran Hung Dao and the Resurgence of Popular Religion in Vietnam*. Bangkok: Mekong Press., 2009.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Taylor, Philip. *Goddess on the Rise: Pilgrimage and Popular Religion in Vietnam*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2004.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Trần, Ngọc Thêm. *Tìm Về Bản Sắc Văn Hóa Việt Nam (discovering Vietnamese Identity)*. Ho Chi Minh City: Tổng hợp., 2001.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Truong, Van Chung. *New Religion: The Cognition and Reality*. Ho Chi Minh City: VNU Publishing House, 2016.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyễn, Hạnh. *Tin Ngưỡng Và Văn Hóa Tin Ngưỡng Ở Việt Nam/beliefs and the Religious Culture in Vietnam*. Ho Chi Minh City: NXB Trẻ, 2012.

Reference: Vietnamese popular religion, Nguyễn, Mạnh Cường. *Văn Hóa Tin Ngưỡng Của Một Số Dân Tộc Trên Đất Việt Nam*. Hanoi: Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa - thông tin & Viện văn hóa, 2008.